

Organophosphoryl Ethanamine Analogues. IV. Synthesis of Methylphosphonic Acid Esters

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In the search for new organophosphorus insecticides and acaricides and to establish the structure-activity relationship, some new methylphosphonates have been synthesised. The LD₅₀ of six of the synthesised compounds were determined and were found to be less toxic than amiton.

THE cholinesterase inhibiting activity of amiton (I)¹, the simplest member of the so-called "Tammelin Esters", is usually high (LD₅₀ p. o. in rat = 3 mg/Kg)². Amiton is seldom used as an acaricide and systemic insecticide because of this high toxicity. A pronounced alteration in the structure of amiton is required to achieve a lower mammalian toxicity. Attempts were made to reduce the basicity of the choline nitrogen by introducing alkoxy carbonyl³, alkoxy sulfonyl⁴ groups or by replacing the basic choline nitrogen by sulphur⁵.

In this investigation an attempt was made to reduce the mammalian toxicity by reducing the electrophilic properties of the phosphoryl group. This led us to synthesise the methylphosphonic esters (II).

X = O, S

R₂ and R₃ = C₂H₅, C₃H₇ (n),

These compounds were synthesised by condensing the methylphosphonic dichloride, CH₃P(O)Cl₂, with

alcohols followed by treating with 2-tertiaryamino-ethanol. The reactions were carried out in the presence of triethylamine to remove the liberated HCl. Compounds (II) are colorless to straw-yellow liquids. However on storage, their colours changed to dark brown. Compounds which contain the piperidino choline moiety undergo solidification to a waxy material within a short time after distillation.

The infrared spectra of all the compounds were recorded as thin films using a sodium chloride window on Unicam SP1200 infrared spectrometer. The infrared spectra of the compounds reveal a strong band at 1250 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to the P=O stretching vibration⁶. Bands in the regions 1300 cm⁻¹ and 950 cm⁻¹ are due to the P-CH₃ stretching vibration⁷.

Biological Activity

The minimum lethal dose (LD₅₀) of six new compounds were determined by injecting intraperitoneally different doses of dilute aqueous solutions of the examined compound in a group of Swiss albino mice of the same sex. The results are recorded in Table 1. When these results are compared with that reported for amiton, it becomes evident that the introduction of the methyl group in compounds (II) directly to the phosphorus atom causes a change of the electrophilic property of the atom and in turn causes a decrease in toxicity. The results also indicate that the most toxic derivatives are the thiolo compounds, i.e., that contain the (P-S-CH₃) bond.

Experimental

Methylphosphonic dichloride used in preparing the compounds was obtained by the pyrolysis of dimethylphosphite, (CH₃O)₂POH, followed by treating the pyrolysate with thionyl chloride and then purified by vacuum distillation⁸.

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TABLE 1—CH₃—P—X—CH₂CH₂NRR'

No.	X	Y	R	R'	b.p. °C (mm Hg)	d ₄ ²⁰	Molecular Formula	Micro analysis%		LD ₅₀ mg/kg
								Calcd.	Found	
1	O	Y ₁	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	82-84 (1.5)	0.9262	C ₁₀ H ₂₄ NO ₃ P	5.9	6.1	—
2	O	Y ₁	C ₂ H ₇	C ₂ H ₇	95-96 (1.1)	0.9852	C ₁₂ H ₂₈ NO ₃ P	5.3	5.2	—
3	O	Y ₁			99-100 (0.8)	—	C ₁₁ H ₂₄ NO ₃ P	5.6	5.8	5.2
4	O	Y ₁	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	110-112 (0.6)	1.2534	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ NO ₃ P	5.2	5.3	—
5	O	Y ₂	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	130-134 (2.0)	0.8261	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ NO ₃ P	5.1	5.0	9.9
6	O	Y ₂	C ₂ H ₇	C ₂ H ₇	96-98 (0.6)	0.8712	C ₁₄ H ₃₀ NO ₃ P	4.6	4.6	13.1
7	O	Y ₂			122-125 (0.8)	—	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ NO ₃ P	4.8	4.8	—
8	O	Y ₂	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	130-132 (0.8)	1.0920	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ NO ₃ P	4.5	4.3	—
9	S	Y ₂	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	90-92 (0.3)	0.9451	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ NO ₂ PS	4.8	4.6	3.7
10	O	Y ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	95-98 (0.3)	1.3271	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ P	10.6	10.6	13.2
11	O	Y ₃			115-118 (0.7)	—	C ₁₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ P	10.1	10.0	—
12	O	Y ₃	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	108-110 (0.5)	1.4251	C ₁₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ P	9.4	9.5	—
13	S	Y ₃	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	114-117 (0.6)	0.8962	C ₁₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ PS	10.0	10.1	4.5

In general these reactions were carried out in an inert solvent such as benzene or petroleum ether.

General method for preparation of the phosphonate esters (1-13).

A mixture of 0.05 mol of the appropriate alcohol and 0.05 mole of triethylamine in 100 ml dry benzene was placed 500 ml round-bottomed, three-necked flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, dropping funnel, and a condenser. The mixture was cooled down to 0-5°. To the cooled mixture, 0.05 mol of methylphosphonic dichloride in 50 ml dry benzene was added with vigorous stirring. A reaction soon began and a finely-divided white precipitate of triethylamine hydrochloride gradually separated. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for another two hours. To this a mixture of 0.05 mol of 2-tertiaryaminoethanol or thioethanol and 0.05 mol of triethylamine in 50 ml dry benzene was added dropwise with stirring. Upon completion of the addition the temperature was gradually raised. Heating was continued for further three hours, keeping the temperature between 60-70°. The

mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and triethylamine HCl was filtered and washed with 50 ml dry benzene. The solvent was then removed and the residue was fractionated under vacuum. The physical data are summarised in Table 1.

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